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Executive Summary

A risk-based human health exposure assessment (HHEA) model was developed to evaluate the exposure for humans in 4 circular economy (CE) routes investigated in 6 of the 7 case studies in the project PROMISCES. The HHEA is a probabilistic tool evaluating the risk posed to human health. The HHEA was applied to the following routes: 1) semi-closed drinking water cycle; 2) groundwater remediation; 3) water reuse for agricultural irrigation; and 4) nutrient recovery. Each of these exposure routes results in a product – drinking water or lettuce – which can be consumed by humans. For some routes, the exposure is purely theoretical, while for others, the entire process chain is investigated in the PROMISCES case study.

The HHEA is built on Bayesian principles and includes Bayesian updating, which enables assessment of risk under conditions of low data availability and high uncertainty. This is particularly useful for evaluation of substances such as PFAS and other industrial persistent, mobile and potentially toxic (iPMT) substances, the removal of which in treatment processes is not yet well studied in literature.

The deliverable explains the different treatments, environmental matrices, and substances which were the focus of the initial assessment. It describes the construction of the HHEA model, with explanations of how different data types – literature data, site specific data, and modelled data – are used to update the prior probability of the removal factor for substances in a process. It also describes how non-technical processes, such as mixing or evaporation, have been included into the treatment trains evaluated. Finally, individual reference quotients for the substances are established, which are used to assess the relative risk of the final concentrations in the products which could be consumed by humans.

In the semi-closed water cycle route, six priority substances (PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFPeS, PFOS, and TFMSA) were identified with risk quotients (RQs) exceeding 1 in the baseline. Scenario analysis revealed that river dilution had the most significant effect on reducing compound concentrations. Additionally, granular activated carbon (GAC) proved effective in lowering risks, regardless of the background contamination level of the water body from which the water for GAC treatment was taken. This finding highlights the importance of both hydrological context and advanced treatment technologies in exposure mitigation.

The model's sensitivity to data type and quality was demonstrated using PFOS, TFMSA, and carbamazepine in the semi-closed water cycle route. While PFOS had abundant but inconsistent literature data, TFMSA and carbamazepine relied on measured values, leading to contrasting outcomes: low removal for TFMSA and high for carbamazepine, particularly in GAC treatment. This underscores the critical role of both measured and literature data in refining risk predictions and reinforces the need for reliable, transferable datasets to reduce uncertainty in PFAS exposure assessments.

For the groundwater remediation route, all compounds showed RQs far above 1 due to assumed high starting concentrations (5 µg/L) and limited removal data. Unlike the other routes, risk here was primarily driven by the initial concentration relative to health-based thresholds. The analysis showed that the more confident we are in high removal efficiency (e.g., through repeated measurements), the higher the allowable starting concentration can be. This emphasizes that model uncertainty

around treatment performance can have a larger influence on risk outcomes than the choice of treatment technology itself.

In the water reuse route, six substances consistently presented RQs above 1 across all percentiles. Scenario analysis showed that for PFOA, inlet concentration played a greater role in risk than treatment variability, while for PFOS, even improved treatment could not bring RQ below 1 due to its reference value. Conversely, in the nutrient recovery route, all seven PFAS compounds had RQs at or below 1 across all percentiles, mainly due to effective removal during membrane filtration, suggesting that risks from this route are comparatively low under current conditions.

A key strength of the HHEA model lies in how it handles epistemic uncertainty—uncertainty stemming from limited or variable data. The model weighs negative findings more heavily in shaping the likelihood and posterior distributions, encouraging precaution in the absence of consistent high-removal evidence. When site-specific measurements are available, the model integrates them randomly with concentration values to avoid under or over estimating risk, supporting more risk-based decision-making. Overall, the HHEA model can be successfully implemented for a variety of available data quantities and end goals, which enables flexible exposure assessment and simplified visualization of which compounds should be prioritized for remediation.

The model is available at <https://github.com/KWB-R/promisces.hhea>.

Table of contents

1. Introduction	11
2. Application in PROMISCES	12
2.1. Model approach.....	12
2.2. PROMISCES exposure routes and initial compounds of interest	12
2.3. Matrix implementation in the HHEA database.....	14
2.4. Treatment implementation in the HHEA database	14
3. Model description.....	16
3.1. Bayesian background	16
3.2. Standard removal process	17
4.2.1 The prior probability	17
4.2.2 Updating the unknown	18
4.2.3 Combining input concentration and removal factors	21
3.3. Mixing and demixing processes	22
3.4. Sewage sludge as an output of wastewater treatment	23
3.5. Producing a reference quotient.....	23
3.6. Model implementation (GitHub)	26
4. Model Application.....	27
4.1. Semi-closed water cycle.....	29
4.1.1. PFOS, TFMSA and carbamazepine: HHEA result interpretation (baseline scenario) ..	32
4.1.2. All substances: baseline scenario and scenario 1	35
4.1.3. Priority substances: comparing different scenarios	37
4.1.4. Priority substances: backwards estimation of tolerable starting concentration	39
4.2. Groundwater remediation.....	40
4.3. Water reuse	44
4.4. Nutrient recovery.....	52
4.5. Code availability.....	62
5. Discussion and conclusions.....	63
6. Literature	65
Annexes.....	67
Annex I. Water reuse simulation outputs.....	67
Annex II. Nutrient recovery simulation outputs	96

List of figures

Figure 1: Semi-closed water cycle exposure route (CS 1 and 2 in PROMISCES).....	13
Figure 2: Groundwater remediation exposure route (CS 6 and 7 in PROMISCES).....	13
Figure 3: Water reuse for agricultural irrigation exposure route (CS 3 in PROMISCES).....	13
Figure 4: Nutrient recovery exposure route (CS 4 in PROMISCES).....	13
Figure 5: Depiction of how parent nodes are connected to a child node via arcs in a Bayesian Network.	16
Figure 6: Beta distribution as the prior for the removal factor.....	18
Figure 7: Schematic overview of how literature data are used (f_{RM} : removal factor, n : number of all available removal factors) to derive the likelihood distribution.....	19
Figure 8: Schematic overview of how case study data are used to derive the likelihood distribution ($f_{RM,i}$: removal factor based on measurement i ; $f_{RM,con}$: overall removal factor including the conservative starting point; n : number of samples).....	21
Figure 9: Semi-closed water cycle exposure route.....	29
Figure 10: Spider plot of the baseline scenario for PFOS, TFMSA, and carbamazepine.	33
Figure 11: Violin plots of posterior removal factor distributions for PFOS (red), TFMSA (orange) and carbamazepine (green) along the treatment processes of the baseline scenario. Treatment IDs were defined in Table 2.	34
Figure 12: Removal factor distribution of drinking water treatment activated carbon for A: PFOS, B: TFMSA and C: carbamazepine	34
Figure 13: Removal factor distributions of primary and secondary wastewater treatment for A: PFOS and B: TFMSA and carbamazepine.	35
Figure 14: Spider plot of the water cycle baseline scenario (GAC as final drinking water treatment)	36
Figure 15: Spider plot of the water cycle scenario 1 (IX as final drinking water treatment)	37
Figure 16: Spider plots of all water cycle scenarios for the priority substances	38
Figure 17: Spider plot of PFOA for different starting concentrations (Baseline scenario).....	39
Figure 18: Groundwater remediation exposure route.....	40
Figure 19: Spider plots of the groundwater remediation (A: persulfate oxidation, B: ultrasonic cavitation) baseline scenario	42
Figure 20: Water reuse exposure route.....	44
Figure 21: Modelled removal factors and concentration profile for PFOA in the water reuse route.....	46
Figure 22: Spider plot for all 14 substances of water reuse route.	47
Figure 23: Modelled PFOA concentration profiles in the water reuse exposure route for the baseline scenario (Std) and 4 adapted scenarios. The reference value is 6 ng/L PFOA.	50
Figure 24: Modelled PFOA RQ for the water reuse exposure route for the baseline scenario (Std) and 4 adapted scenarios.	51

Figure 25: Nutrient recovery exposure route.....	52
Figure 26: Modelled removal factors and concentration profile of nutrient recovery route for PFOA.	55
Figure 27: Spider plot for all 7 PFAS in nutrient recovery route.....	56
Figure 28: Modelled concentration profiles of nutrient recovery route – scenarios 1 to 4. Reference value is estimated at 6 ng/L PFOA.	61
Figure 29: Modelled reference quotient diagram along the nutrient recovery route for PFOA in 4 different scenarios.	62

List of tables

Table 1: Explanation of matrices used in the HHEA.	14
Table 2: Treatment processes used in the HHEA.....	15
Table 3: Example of how likelihood and posterior distributions are affected based on different types of literature data evaluated.....	20
Table 4: Reference values used in the HHEA. For drinking water, the EU DWD PFAS-20 limit of 100 ng/L was divided first by 20 and then by the individual compound’s RPF. * = (Commission., 2020; Umweltbundesamt., 2023).....	25
Table 5: Scenarios assessed for the exposure routes. Bold text denotes changes from the baseline. (Treatment IDs as defined in Table 2).....	28
Table 6: Maximum concentration, reference value and starting concentration of substances assessed for the water cycle exposure route	30
Table 7: Removal factors derived from experimental data of CS1.....	31
Table 8: Dilution characteristics of the water cycle baseline scenario.....	32
Table 9: Maximum tolerable starting concentrations in the baseline scenario.....	40
Table 10: Derived removal factors for persulfate based chemical oxidation and ultrasonic cavitation, from as yet unpublished PROMISCES deliverables.....	41
Table 11: Tolerable starting concentrations in the groundwater remediation scenarios and the effect of persulfate based oxidation.	43
Table 12: List of 10 PFAS and 4 iPMT that have been considered for the water reuse route.	44
Table 13: Variable definition for water reuse route – PFOA example.	45
Table 14: implemented starting concentrations for water reuse route.	45
Table 15: Mixing process characteristics for the water reuse route for all scenarios.	46
Table 16: Changing parameters for the different water reuse scenarios.	48
Table 17: Variable definition for nutrient recovery route.....	52
Table 18: implemented starting concentrations for the nutrient recovery route:.....	53
Table 19: Characteristics of mixing processes of the nutrient recovery route.	54
Table 20: Changing parameters for the different scenarios of the nutrient recovery route.....	57

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
HHEA	Human health exposure assessment
CE	Circular economy
iPMT	industrial persistent, mobile and potentially toxic compounds
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
CS	Case study
BN	Bayesian network
RF	Removal factor
LOD	Limit of detection
RQ	Reference quotient
TDI	Tolerable daily intake
BCF	Bioconcentration factor
RPF	Relative potency factor
GAC	Granular activated carbon
DOC	Dissolved organic carbon
DBP	Dibutyl phthalate
DEP	Diethyl phthalate
PFNA	Perfluorononanoic acid
PFOS	Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid
PFOA	Perfluorooctanoic acid
PFHxA	Perfluorohexanoic acid

1. Introduction

This deliverable serves as a guidance document on the risk-based human health exposure assessment (HHEA) developed in PROMISCES, formerly called the human health risk assessment model.

The HHEA is applied to 4 circular economy (CE) exposure routes which are relevant for human health: 1) semi-closed drinking water cycle; 2) groundwater remediation; 3) water reuse for agricultural irrigation; and 4) nutrient recovery. The fifth CE route investigated in PROMISCES – material recovery from dredged sediments for eco-materials – was deemed to not have notable potential exposures for human health, and therefore this route was not investigated in the HHEA. The HHEA aims to ultimately improve understanding of decision making and risk management under uncertainty related to fate, exposure, and hazard, and quantify the overall epistemic uncertainty related to the exposure assessments.

This is accomplished by using a probabilistic approach for determining a reference quotient for each compound investigated in the exposure route. By using probability distributions and Bayesian updating to calculate prior distributions, likelihood distributions, and posterior distributions to describe the percent removal in a technical treatment step, in combination with dilution or removal in a natural treatment step, the full distribution of the risk to human health present in the final media (drinking water or lettuce) can be evaluated by evaluating multiple percentiles (50th, 75th, 95th, 99th). This facilitates a higher resolution assessment of when a possible exceedance of risk could occur.

The HHEA model can be used by operators of parts of the exposure routes, including operators of wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) or drinking water treatment plants (DWTP), groundwater wells, and landfill leachate treatment plants (LLTP). However, the model can be extended beyond the individual treatment steps included in the routes investigated herein. In this way, the model can be applied for any exposure route of interest. The model is freely available on GitHub (<https://github.com/KWB-R/promisces.hhea>), runs on Python, and can be downloaded to a local environment and used without an internet connection.

2. Application in PROMISCES

2.1. Model approach

The HHEA describes the concentration of a substance (in this case, a chemical compound) along a process chain, hereby known as an exposure route. A process can be technical, such as removal during a specific technical treatment, or natural, such as degradation in soil or groundwater. For technical processes a removal, or concentration decrease, can be described by a removal factor between 0 and 100%. For mixing processes, such as dilution by “clean” water or concentration due to evaporating water, the mass balance must be considered. A removal factor can be calculated using the pollutant concentration before and after the mixing or separation process. This can lead to negative removal factors under certain circumstances. At the end of the simulation, the substance’s concentration is divided by a reference value (i.e. a guideline value for the substance in a media) to obtain the reference quotient, which indicates whether the consumer might be negatively affected by the substance.

One major goal of the HHEA was the ability to perform calculations with little data or knowledge, since the behaviour and the effect of many of the assessed PFAS and iPMT compounds is largely unknown. In PROMISCES, this knowledge gap will be narrowed and the new findings will be implemented into the HHEA.

To achieve this, a probabilistic approach was chosen, in which a prior probability distribution can be updated by either or both literature and sample data in a Bayesian manner. The prior distribution ensures that the worst case scenario (no substance removal) is considered until there is sufficient proof of removal available. Therefore, what is described in this report is known as a risk-based human health exposure assessment.

2.2. PROMISCES exposure routes and initial compounds of interest

First, to ensure that the 4 CE exposure routes being investigated had been correctly outlined for subsequent modelling work, the appropriate case study (CS) leaders were contacted and the correct order of treatment steps in each CE route was confirmed. The four exposure routes investigated are presented in Figures 1-4. Two routes end with human exposure via consuming lettuce (Figure 3 and Figure 4), and two routes end with human exposure via drinking water (Figure 1 and Figure 2). All 4 routes were theoretical in nature, with certain treatments investigated in PROMISCES’ case studies, as well as some treatments which were included to evaluate the theoretical exposure which could occur. The theoretical treatments are explained in the individual route explanations in section 5 of the deliverable.

Figure 1: Semi-closed water cycle exposure route (CS 1 and 2 in PROMISCES).

Figure 2: Groundwater remediation exposure route (CS 6 and 7 in PROMISCES).

Figure 3: Water reuse for agricultural irrigation exposure route (CS 3 in PROMISCES).

Figure 4: Nutrient recovery exposure route (CS 4 in PROMISCES).

2.3. Matrix implementation in the HHEA database

The water matrix can change significantly along the treatment train of the four exposure routes. In total, 14 different water matrices were implemented and defined in the HHEA model (Table 1). The matrix information is used for two reasons: i) to obtain a starting concentration from literature data if required, and ii) as a quality control measure of the exposure route to ensure that treatment steps and treatment input are consistent and treatment processes are in a correct order. A starting concentration for different matrices can be found, for example, in the risk assessment part of the Decision Support Framework (DSF), which has been developed in PROMISCES (<https://promisces.eu/Results/Tools/PROMISCES+DSF.html>).

Table 1: Explanation of matrices used in the HHEA.

Matrix ID	Matrix Name	Description
iww	Industrial wastewater	Raw wastewater from industrial sources
hww	Household wastewater	Raw wastewater from households
lww	Landfill leachate	Raw wastewater from landfill
rww	Raw wastewater	Raw wastewater from various sources (dominated by household wastewater)
tww	Treated wastewater	Wastewater after at least primary and secondary treatment
tiw	Treated industrial wastewater	Industrial or landfill leachate after wastewater treatment (not further specified, only used for site-specific data)
stw	Stormwater runoff	Urban stormwater runoff
raw	Rainwater	Wet atmospheric deposition (rainwater without runoff)
suw	Surface water	
grw	Groundwater	
pow	Soil porewater	Porewater after mixing with irrigation water
bfw	Bank filtrate	
drw	Drinking water	Water after drinking water treatment
sdg	Dewatered sludge	Dewatered sludge from treated wastewater (as part of the secondary wastewater treatment)

2.4. Treatment implementation in the HHEA database

The four exposure routes contain a total of 20 processes, all of which were implemented in the HHEA model (Table 2). Each process has a unique ID that can be used to integrate it into the model. Furthermore, input and output matrices are listed and explained in more detail in Table 2. In the column Output Matrix in Table 1, "no_change" means that the matrix did not change as a result of the processes.

The standard removal algorithm (explained in section 4.3) was used for all technical processes except for the thickening and dewatering of sludge as part of wastewater treatment. The dewatering of sewage sludge is a special case that is closely linked to the primary and secondary wastewater treatment processes and is explained in section 4.5. The integration of dilution and separation processes is described in section 4.4.

Table 2: Treatment processes used in the HHEA.

ID	Name	Input Matrix	Output Matrix
wwt1	Primary wastewater treatment (mechanical and physical treatment)	rww, iww, hww, stw, lww	no_change
wwt2	Secondary wastewater treatment	rww, iww, hww, stw, lww	tww
wwtt	Combination of primary and secondary wastewater treatment	rww, iww, hww, stw, lww	tww
wwsl	Sludge production after primary and secondary wastewater treatment	rww, hww	sdg
wwco	Tertiary wastewater treatment: Coagulation and filtration	tww, iww	tww
wwuf	Tertiary wastewater treatment: Ultrafiltration	tww, iww	tww
wwnf	Tertiary wastewater treatment: Nanofiltration	tww, iww	tww
wwro	Tertiary wastewater treatment: Reverse Osmosis	tww, iww	tww
wwel	Tertiary wastewater treatment: Electro-oxidation (e-peroxone)	tww, iww	tww
wwmb	Tertiary wastewater treatment: Membrane bioreactor	tww, iww	tww
grpf	Groundwater treatment: Persulfate-based in situ chemical oxidation - (n)ZVI + Fe(VI)	grw	no_change
gruc	Groundwater treatment: ultrasonic cavitation	grw	no_change
gren	Groundwater treatment: catalysis by extra cellular ligninolytic enzymes	grw	grw
npbk	Natural Process: Bank filtration	suw	bfw
wetl	Additional treatment: Constructed wetlands	rww, iww, hww, stw, tww, lww	tww
dwae	Drinking water treatment: aeration	suw, bfw, grw, drw, tww, stw	drw
dwrfl	Drinking water treatment: rapid filtration	suw, bfw, grw, drw, tww, stw	drw
dwac	Drinking water treatment: granular activated carbon	suw, bfw, grw, drw, tww, stw	drw
dwex	Drinking water treatment: anion exchange	suw, bfw, grw, drw, tww, stw	drw
dilsw	Dilution by surface water	tww, stw	suw
dilww	Dilution by municipal wastewater	iww, lww, rww, tww	rww
dilgw	Dilution by groundwater	bfw, pow	grw
dilrw	Dilution by soil irrigation water (rain water)	suw, tww, stw, sdg	pow
dilpr	Dilution by process water (from minor secondary stream)	tww, iww, hww, rww, lww, drw, grw	no_change
sepev	Separation due to evaporation	suw, pow	no_change
	NaturalProcess: Degradation in groundwater (biotic and abiotic)		

3. Model description

3.1. Bayesian background

The HHEA was originally foreseen as a probabilistic Bayesian network (BN). BNs are probabilistic graphical models in which variables (nodes) are connected to each other via arcs (arrows) going from parent to child nodes (Martinez-Megias et al., 2023). An example can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Depiction of how parent nodes are connected to a child node via arcs in a Bayesian Network.

Each node has a set of possible states (parameters, values, etc.) that occur with a certain probability. The probabilities of the states are known as beliefs. The nodes are described using probability distributions, which can be fit to existing information such as expert knowledge, experimental data, literature data, or a mix of data sources. This fitting of some type of existing information to a probability distribution produces a prior probability. The arcs represent conditional probability tables, which define the relationship between the parent and child nodes and how they change.

Using the belief and the established network, Bayesian inferencing using Bayes' theorem can be used to calculate the risk at the end of the exposure route. Bayes' theorem (Equation 1) calculates the posterior probability (of the child A given the parent B, given the prior probability of the child, the marginal probability of the parent , and the likelihood of the child given a fixed state of the parent.

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(B|A) * P(A)}{P(B)} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Using this equation, BNs can show different states of nodes as they are updated with more data (belief updating) and different types of data. BNs are easy to visualize and understand by non-technical audiences. They are also suitable for small and incomplete data sets (Uusitalo, 2007), which makes them applicable for conducting risk assessments of iPMT and PFAS in CE routes.

In the process of tool development, a Bayesian network was foregone for a probabilistic tool with Bayesian updating. The benefit of a Bayesian network, namely that it allows backwards inferencing, was difficult to implement in this tool due to the low data availability, and lack of experimental data in comparison to literature data. Additionally, a Bayesian network requires data to be discretized into categories, which would further reduce the resolution with which results could be analysed for the CE routes explored herein. Therefore, it was decided to keep the tool as a probabilistic model with Bayesian updating. However, upgrading to a Bayesian network could be done in the future.

3.2. Standard removal process

For most of the technical treatment processes, the output concentration can be estimated by using an input concentration and a removal factor (RF), as seen in Equation 2. This is the standard procedure in the HHEA model.

$$c_{out} = c_{in} (1 - RF) \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

The input concentration is either a single value, a uniform distribution by a range defined as starting concentration, or the result of the simulation of previous processes. The removal factor distribution is built by prior and likelihood distributions. The procedure is described in detail in the following sections.

4.2.1 The prior probability

The overall goal of the risk-based HHEA is not to estimate the most probable substance concentration along the exposure route, but to describe the final risk of exceeding a reference value. The risk is the result of the impact of a negative effect and its likelihood to occur, and is described by Equation 3.

$$\text{Risk} = \text{Likelihood} \times \text{Impact} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

The knowledge about both parts of the aforementioned equation must be considered. An unacceptable risk occurs when:

- given a certain impact, the likelihood is too high or unknown
- given a certain likelihood, the impact is too high or unknown

The prior distribution determines how much information is needed to prove low risk. Therefore, it is the most important assumption for assessing situations where knowledge or data is insufficient.

For the PROMISCES HHEA, the prior for the removal within one process was required to meet the following criteria:

1. the distribution needs to be symmetric - high and low removal must be equally likely – to avoid an initial bias.
2. Both options - complete removal and no removal - must be included in the distribution.

Furthermore, regarding the process chain, the following must be true:

1. For several subsequent processes with unknown removal, the outcome “no removal at all” must not be excluded.
2. Each additional process with unknown but potential removal must result in a lower final risk.

The most intuitive choice for the prior would be a uniform distribution, which represents every removal factor as equally likely if nothing is known about the removal factor. However, drawing from a uniform distribution between 0 and 1 leads to very few values close to 0% removal. This would mean that for several subsequent processes with no information on the removal factor, there would

be no scenario with repeatedly 0% removal in every process step, unless the number of samples drawn from the distributions is (inefficiently) large. Thus, a worst case scenario cannot be modelled by a uniform distribution.

Instead, a convex shaped beta distribution was chosen as prior for the removal factors (Figure 6). The beta distribution is described by two parameters, alpha and beta, and is only defined for values between 0 and 1. It is symmetric when both of its parameters are equal (criterion 1). For alpha and beta below 1, the density increases towards both 0 and 1 (criterion 2). This distribution favours low or high removal and reduces the weights of intermediate values. For removal factors, this means that best case and worst case removal scenarios are favoured by default. This way, even long treatment chains contain the option “no removal at all” with a reasonable amount of samples drawn (criterion 3), while at the same time, the average risk decreases with every process step (criterion 4).

Figure 6: Beta distribution as the prior for the removal factor.

4.2.2 Updating the unknown

According to Bayes’ theorem (Equation 1), the posterior distribution describes the final probability of one process. It is a combination of the prior assumption and the likelihood based on observations. For the HHEA, the prior can be updated either by literature and/or by on-site sample data. All removal factors provided for the literature or site based likelihood distribution must be integers and expressed as a percentage (%). Sometimes, only qualitative statements about the substance removal are available in literature. The qualitative statement “no removal observed” and “no significant removal observed” are added as 0% and 5% removal, respectively. The posterior of a removal factor is proportional to the prior, multiplied by the likelihood based on literature data and the likelihood based on measured data.

Updating the prior with literature data

Literature data from a study is only transferable to a limited extent to other locations. Varying environmental conditions or technical specifications have a large impact on the removal factor. In most cases, the potential variation between two identical processes at two different locations is larger than the variation within one location. Thus, the suitability of a removal factor from an external data source for the current assessment cannot be estimated by the standard deviation of the factor

or other statistical dispersion parameters. In other words: regardless of the spread of removal factors at two different sites, the mean or median at one site can still be informative. For that reason, only one value per site, such as a location parameter like the mean or median, is considered in the literature likelihood (Figure 7).

In reviews or meta studies (i.e. a study evaluating the results of other studies), single results are often aggregated into ranges. Here, for the reason explained above, instead of using the range of a meta study, it is necessary to list the results of single studies separately. In addition to the literature data, a conservative starting point (the conservative removal factor) is included to account for the amount of knowledge involved. It can be described as the mean of all included removal factors and 0.1% removal. If the number of literature data is low, the conservative removal factor is significantly lower than the actual mean value of all removal factors found in the literature. As the number of data increases, the conservative removal factor gets closer to the actual mean of the literature data. The more data available, the less conservative the likelihood becomes. Three examples are listed in Table 3 to explain the approach.

Figure 7: Schematic overview of how literature data are used (f_{RM} : removal factor, n : number of all available removal factors) to derive the likelihood distribution.

Table 3: Example of how likelihood and posterior distributions are affected based on different types of literature data evaluated.

Example	1 study 80% removal	5 studies 80% removal	1 study 20% removal
Figure			
Explanation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High impact of the conservative removal factor on the likelihood • Broad likelihood distribution • The prior dominates the shape of the posterior, but it's no longer symmetric • Shift towards higher probability of complete removal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low impact of the conservative removal factor on the likelihood • Very strong evidence that the removal factor is indeed somewhere around 80% • The likelihood dominates the shape of the posterior 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One study with 20% removal has a stronger effect on the posterior than one study with 80% removal • Risk-based approach: more evidence is needed to verify a high removal

Updating the prior with site specific data

The prior distribution can also be updated with experimental data generated directly in the particular exposure route in PROMISCES. This data is understandably most suitable for the specific CE exposure route. If it is available, the prior is updated in two stages: first by literature data and then by case study data. However, a decision on whether to use only case study data if literature data insufficiently reflect the process can also be taken. This can occur when a case study process is optimized for the removal of a specific substance, while literature data is based on a general process setup. Similar to the procedure for updating using literature data explained above, a likelihood for the measured data must also be derived. Instead of using aggregated values, every removal factor measured in the case study will be included in the likelihood, which gives more weight to the site specific results (Figure 8). If literature data is included, the posterior distribution is then calculated as the product of the prior distribution and two likelihood distributions, one based on literature data, and based on case study data.

Concentrations measured below the limit of detection (LOD) can be considered as complete removal, i.e. a removal factor of 100%. The conservative starting point requires a large amount of measurements below LOD in order to have a high impact on the posterior distribution.

Figure 8: Schematic overview of how case study data are used to derive the likelihood distribution ($f_{RM,i}$: removal factor based on measurement i ; $f_{RM,con}$: overall removal factor including the conservative starting point; n : number of samples).

Updating the prior with model data

Many natural and technical processes can be described with various types of models. A major advantage of modelling is that input variables can be quickly adjusted and new results can be generated. The number of possible model results is therefore easily many times higher than measurement results. On the other hand, measurement results often represent reality better than models. One example is a model that describes the removal of a substance by GAC, where the removal efficiency is dependent on the bed volume and the DOC content of the water, among other things. It would be possible to calculate numerous results by varying the input variables. Feeding all the model results into the HHEA model would dominate the posterior removal factor distribution due to the amount of data available. Instead, calculating only two results is suggested: i) based on average conditions; and ii) adjusted to the specific conditions of the case study. Using this approach, one model will have exactly the same weight as one literature study or one on-site measurement.

4.2.3 Combining input concentration and removal factors

The HHEA combines two important aspects from the literature and the experiments in PROMISCES: concentration and removal percentages of substances in the different steps of the exposure routes. This section explains how these two aspects are utilized in the HHEA.

The input concentration of a substance and the removal factor of a process can either be paired randomly, or sorted so that the lowest removal factor is paired with the highest initial concentration and vice versa (worst case and best case scenarios). Although the sorting (worst case and best case) seems to fit to the idea of conservative risk assessment, it may lead to an unjustifiable overestimation of risk.

Therefore, two different methods for data pairing were implemented in the HHEA model:

1. **If the difference in removal factors is expected to average out over time, removal factors and input concentrations are combined randomly.** Example case 1: Raw wastewater concentrations are paired with the removal in a WWTP over 1 year – as it's highly unlikely that the highest influent concentration and the lowest WWTP removal would be consistently paired over the course of the whole year, random pairing is allowed.

- 2. Removal factors and input concentrations are paired in a best case and worst case manner.**
 Example case 2: Data from two different treatment plants show different removals (30% removal and 60% removal), for which some site specific variability is known (i.e. different ozone doses). If the removal factor would be applied randomly, this systematic difference would be ignored. Therefore, input concentrations and removal factors are paired so that the best case and worst case scenarios are assessed.

In general, data that is gathered in the case studies can be assumed to average out over time and are paired randomly (example case 1), while literature data can have systematic site specific deviation and are assessed for best case and worst case scenarios (example case 2). During the simulation, the dominant input distribution is defined for each posterior distribution. If this is the site specific case study data, method 1 is applied. The site specific data is assumed to be dominant if the mode of the likelihood is less than 5% away from the mode of the resulting posterior. The 5% was selected based on the frequently used limit of 5% as the significance level: if the difference between the two modes is less than 5%, then it is not significant.

3.3. Mixing and demixing processes

In several processes, different types of water are mixed (e.g. effluent into surface water, bank filtrate into groundwater) or separated (e.g. evaporation from soil pore water).

The output concentration of a mixture of two waters is defined in Equation 4:

$$c_{out} = c_{in}x_{in} + c_2x_2 \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

where c_{in} is the concentration in the input, c_{out} is the concentration in the final water, x_{in} is the according proportion in the input, and x_2 is the proportion being mixed. The sum of x_{in} and x_2 is equal to 1. Equation 4 is also the basis for the separation process, where a proportion of the input water (x_2) leaves the system with concentration c_2 .

The remaining substance is thus concentrated in the output. This can be described by Equation 5:

$$c_{out} = \frac{c_{in} - c_2x_2}{x_{out}} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

All mixing and demixing data are very site specific and cannot be substituted with literature data. Conversely, it is assumed that mixing or demixing always averages out, and process parameters are randomly combined with the process input concentration.

Both proportions sum up to one, so only one proportion x_2 and optionally a corresponding concentration c_2 need to be provided. For standard removal, the mixing and demixing are applied in a probabilistic way. Data can be entered either as mean and standard deviation, or as minimum and maximum proportion or concentration. Regardless of the type of values provided, a normal distribution is created. The range between a minimum and maximum value is therefore interpreted as a 95% interval of a normal distribution. The normal distribution of the water proportion and the concentration is truncated at 0 and 1, and at 0 ng/L. For the separation process, the distribution is also cut off at the highest possible concentration, which corresponds to the water mixture as it enters the process.

3.4. Sewage sludge as an output of wastewater treatment

Substances can be removed from the water matrix during the primary and secondary wastewater treatment by

- mechanical elimination;
- biological degradation; or
- sorption to sludge followed by sludge separation.

For PFAS and other iPMTs, mechanical removal and biodegradation play a minor role. If any removal occurs, it is usually due to sorption to sludge. Sludge thickening and dewatering can be seen as a separation process, in which treated wastewater is separated from a matrix containing a higher proportion of solids. Thus, it is also based on Equation 6, where the concentration of the separated liquid phase is equal to the secondary wastewater treatment effluent concentration. The distribution of the concentration in the effluent can be obtained by applying the standard removal process for primary and secondary wastewater treatment (wwtt).

$$c_{sludge} = \frac{c_{in} - (1 - RF)c_{in}(1 - x_{sludge})}{x_{sludge}} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

A sludge volume of 10% of the inflow volume of raw wastewater is assumed as an average. A standard deviation of 2% is added to account for variations between different treatment plants.

For degradable substances or substances removed to a significant extent by mechanical wastewater treatment, calculating sludge concentration within the HHEA approach is much more complicated and was therefore not implemented.

3.5. Producing a reference quotient

The final output concentrations are compared to a reference value stemming from international or national guidelines. Equation 7 was used to derive a reference quotient (RQ):

$$\text{Reference quotient (RQ)} = \frac{c_{out}}{\text{Reference value}} \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

For exposure routes ending in drinking water, the latest European drinking water directive (Directive 2020/2184) value for PFAS-20 of 100 ng/L was used to derive a reference value for each individual PFAS. 100 ng/L were first divided by 20 which results in an effective single substance fraction of 5 ng/L. Relative potency factors (RPF), which quantify the effect of a single substance compared to PFOA, which has the RPF = 1, were used. By dividing the PFOA fraction of 5 ng/L by the RPF, an effectively equivalent reference value is obtained for the individual substances. The RPF and the derived reference values are given in Table 4 and come from (RIVM., 2023). Use of the RPFs enables the HHEA to consider in vivo endpoints of the individual PFAS and further substances which are not part of the PFAS-20 sum of the directive can be included in the assessment.

It is important to note that the HHEA is **only applicable for liquid media**. A concentration in other matrices, like plant tissue, cannot be simulated with this approach. Instead of calculating the whole pathway from irrigation water or sludge to human crop consumption (relevant for the nutrient

recovery and water reuse for agricultural irrigation exposure routes), a reference value for soil pore water was calculated backwards, starting with the tolerable daily intake (TDI) was available for PFOA (Schrenk et al., 2020) and for dibutyl phthalate (DBP) (Silano V, 2019). To obtain the TDI of individual substances, the same procedure was applied as for obtaining the drinking water reference values. The TDI was calculated for a person weighing 70 kg. It was further assumed that the food under consideration should contribute only 10% to the TDI value (e.g. a safety factor for other sources). To calculate the pore water concentration, the average daily consumption of vegetables (0.26 kg according to (Ministerio de Medio Ambiente, 2007)) and the bioconcentration factor (BCF) from the soil pore water to the plant foliage were also required (Figure 10). TDI and BCF are substance-specific values (in silico endpoints), whereas the remaining values in Equation 8 were applicable for substances considered.

$$c_{pw} = \frac{TDI \left[\frac{ng}{kg * d} \right] \times 70[kg]}{0.26 \left[\frac{kg}{d} \right] \times BCF \left[\frac{L}{kg} \right]} \times 10\% \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

If a TDI was not available, relative potency factors (RPF) were used when available. For the PFAS compounds, RPF list by (RIVM., 2023) was considered. These RPFs quantify toxicity relative to PFOA (index compound), converting mixed PFAS exposures into PFOA equivalents and assuming dose additivity for shared toxicological endpoints.

There was no TDI or RPF for diethyl phthalate, carbamazepine and diuron. In such cases, pore water reference concentration was calculated according to US Environmental Protection Agency methodology (EPA., 1989) with exposure parameters established by Spanish Law (Estado., 2003; Ministerio de Medio Ambiente, 2007)) and toxicological data from several sources (Health., 2013; RAIS., 2025; TCEQ., 2023). It should be noted that, although reference values were derived for this analysis, this was not one of the main objectives of the intended work. For substances for which there were no published reference values, other regulatory values could have been considered, such as those from the EU Drinking Water Directive 2020/2184 (Commission., 2020). However, we chose to derive them to avoid an extremely conservative approach and to better illustrate the correct functioning of the developed tool with more realistic thresholds.

BCF values were obtained from (Felizeter, 2020) for most of the PFAS. If BCF value was not available for a substance, it was estimated that an average of 150 L of irrigation water is needed to obtain 1 kg of lettuce. Reference values used for the different water matrices evaluated in the HHEA can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4: Reference values used in the HHEA. For drinking water, the EU DWD PFAS-20 limit of 100 ng/L was divided first by 20 and then by the individual compound's RPF. * = (Commission., 2020; Umweltbundesamt., 2023)

Substance	RPF	Reference value in drinking water (ng/L)	Reference value in pore water (ng/L)
PFAS-20	100	100	
PFBA	0.05	100	5
PFPeA	0.05	100	5
PFHxA	0.01	500	3
PFHpA	1	5	6
PFOA	1	5	6
PFNA	10	0.5	0.3
PFDA	10	0.5	0.003
PFBS	0.001	5000	1692
PFPeS	0.6	8.3	
PFHxS	0.6	8.3	0.05
PFHpS	2	2.5	
PFOS	2	2.5	0.3
PFDS	2	2.5	0.6
GenX	0.06	83	
DONA	0.03	167	
6:2 FTOH	0.02	250	
8:2 FTOH	0.04	125	
TFA	0.002	2500	
4:2 FTSA	0.05	100	
6:2 FTSA	1	5	
8:2 FTSA	10	0.5	
Benzotriazole	-	3000*	
Diethyl phthalate	-		150000
Dibutyl phthalate	-		1800
Carbamazepine	-	300	240
Diuron	-		370

3.6. Model implementation (GitHub)

To simulate exposures with different treatment steps, a flexible model implementation for initial matrices and input concentrations was required. In addition to using the aforementioned FAKIN naming conventions, the process of including new information into the shared database was controlled to ensure consistency. First, separate .csv files were used for collecting the different information. Then, the content of the tables was translated into Python source code as collections of class objects. Three different classes - “Matrices”, “Substances” and “Treatments” - which contained the IDs and descriptions of all integrated water matrices, pollutants and treatment steps were created.

An example of how to run a simulation is given in the jupyter notebook “basic_hhea.ipynb”, which is available in the GitHub repository (<https://github.com/KWB-R/promisces.hhea>). Depending on the initial matrix and the substance to be assessed, the tool first searches for a starting concentration in the literature data. The process steps are run in a subsequent loop. For each process, literature and case study removal data are combined as described in the previous sections and passed to a function that simulates the output concentration of the treatment process. Based on the data type, the removal factors are either sorted or not (see section 3.1), after which the removal is applied to the input concentration. The output concentration is returned once all treatment processes have been simulated. Finally, the result of the exposure assessment is compared to a reference value, and a reference quotient is calculated. To be able to retrace the simulation of an exposure scenario, the input data and all intermediate results are returned together with the final result.

The “result_summary” Excel file provides a summary of the concentration profile, the removal factor at each treatment step, and additional information about the simulation, such as the number of runs, the water matrices, or the data treatment (see section 3.3). Furthermore, two violin plots are created, describing the substance concentration and the removal factors along the treatment train.

A .png figure shows the evolution of the prior to the posterior distribution of removal factor based on the available data. This is crucial for understanding the impact of data on the removal calculations. To do so, the range of both the modelled concentrations and modelled removal factors is visualized in violin plots during assessment of the CE routes, enabling the user to evaluate whether the correct range for each process was used in the assessment.

4. Model Application

This section explains the data, assumptions, and methods used for each of the 4 CE routes investigated. The initial plan was to assess the final risk based on only in silico vs only in vitro toxicity endpoints for 10-15 compounds of greatest concern for each CE route. However, as the HHEA model is dependent upon the experimental data from PROMISCES CS, it was not possible to analyse at least 10 compounds for each CS route. The analysed compounds are as follows:

- Semi-closed water cycle: 14 compounds from (Rückbeil et al., 2025)
- Groundwater remediation: 15 compounds from Deliverable 3.2
- Water reuse: 14 compounds from (Meijide Fernández et al., 2025)
- Nutrient recovery: 7 compounds from (Lancioni et al., 2023)

By simulating different scenarios for each CE route, several questions can be answered, such as:

- a. What is the most critical substance?
- b. Under which circumstances can a substance pose a risk?
- c. Is further treatment required?

Scenarios are compared by statistically analysing the results in percentiles and dividing results by the reference value to obtain a reference quotient (RQ). If the maximum RQ of the concentration distribution is below 1, the reference value will certainly be met. If not, the RQ for different percentiles is calculated and displayed in a spider plot (Figure 10). The outer circle of the spider plot defines the 50th percentile, and the inner circle defines the 99th percentile of the concentration distribution. The value of the RQ is depicted using a color scale from green to red for easier understanding of exceedance.

In this report, the HHEA model is demonstrated and explained in detail using the baseline scenario of the semi-closed water cycle exposure route. For all other simulated scenarios, results are displayed in a compressed format. The baseline scenarios were used to identify the substances of highest concern for each exposure route. The scenarios are either based on the current status of a PROMISCES case study, or on the expected characteristics of the treatment train to be installed. For priority substances, further scenarios in which certain parts of the exposure route were altered, were run. All scenarios assessed are depicted in Table 5.

Table 5: Scenarios assessed for the exposure routes. Bold text denotes changes from the baseline. (Treatment IDs as defined in Table 2)

Route	Baseline	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4
Semi-closed drinking water cycle	River size: small River background concentration: clean Final drinking water treatment: dwac	River size: small River background concentration: clean Final drinking water treatment: dwex	River size: large River background concentration: contaminated Final drinking water treatment: dwac	River size: large River background concentration: clean Final drinking water treatment: dwac	River size: small River background concentration: contaminated Final drinking water treatment: dwac
Groundwater remediation	Groundwater: contaminated Groundwater remediation process: Persulfate/Ferrate Removal efficiency: by experimental data	Groundwater: contaminated Groundwater remediation process: Ultrasonic Cavitation Removal efficiency: by experimental data	Groundwater: contaminated Groundwater remediation process: Any process Removal efficiency: poor (10%)	Groundwater: contaminated Groundwater remediation process: None Removal efficiency: -	
Agricultural water reuse	Raw wastewater: average concentrations E-peroxonne performance: Average	Raw wastewater: high concentrations E-peroxonne performance: poor	Raw wastewater: low concentrations E-peroxonne performance: poor	Raw wastewater: high concentrations E-peroxonne performance: good	Raw wastewater: low concentrations E-peroxonne performance: good
Nutrient recovery	Raw wastewater: average concentrations Leachate treatment: average Nanofiltration: average Municipal WWT: 30% (estimated parameter with mean expected porosity).	Raw wastewater: average concentrations Leachate treatment: poor Nanofiltration: poor Municipal WWT: poor	Raw wastewater: average concentrations Leachate treatment: good Nanofiltration: poor Municipal WWT: poor	Raw wastewater: average concentrations Leachate treatment: poor Nanofiltration: good Municipal WWT: poor	Raw wastewater: average concentrations Leachate treatment: good Nanofiltration: good Municipal WWT: poor

GAC = granular activated carbon; IX= ion exchange; N/E = not evaluated; WWT= wastewater treatment

4.1. Semi-closed water cycle

The water cycle exposure pathway consists of wastewater treatment, bank filtration, and drinking water treatment. More specifically, the wastewater treatment considered is a combination of primary and secondary treatment, followed by coagulation and filtration, while the drinking water treatment includes aeration, rapid filtration and either granular activated carbon filtration (GAC) or anion exchange (IX). In addition to the treatments, two dilution processes are part of the water cycle: dilution by surface water and dilution by groundwater. For the baseline scenario, both dilution waters were assumed to not be contaminated (PFAS concentrations of 0 ng/L) and GAC was used as final drinking water treatment. The exposure route can be seen again in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Semi-closed water cycle exposure route.

The following substances were assessed in this exposure route: PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFBS, PFPeS, PFHxS, PFOS, TFMSA, benzotriazole and carbamazepine. The selection was based on the availability of removal data for the final drinking water treatment (taken from (Rückbeil et al., 2025)). (Table 6). At CS1 a starting concentration for benzotriazole and carbamazepine was defined, As there were no measurements available from PROMISCES CS1, the maximum substance concentration from literature data was used as a worst-case assumption. There was no literature data in the database for PFPeS, and trifluoromethanesulfonic acid (TFMSA) The starting concentration for PFPeS was set to 100 times the reference value. Since no reference value for TFMSA was found, it was decided to perform the exposure assessment in a relative way, where the reference value is defined as 1 and the starting concentration is defined as a factor of 100 to this.

Table 6: Maximum concentration, reference value and starting concentration of substances assessed for the water cycle exposure route

Substance	Maximum concentration in raw wastewater in ng/L	Reference value, ng/L	Numbers of studies	Starting concentration HHEA, ng/L
PFBA	19	100	31	19
PFPeA	27	100	33	27
PFHxA	270	500	67	270
PFHpA	58	5	64	58
PFOA	550	5	88	550
PFNA	26.4	0.5	69	26.4
PFDA	27	0.5	56	27
PFBS	37	5000	52	37
PFPeS	-	8.3	-	830
PFHxS	54	8.3	38	54
PFOS	449	2.5	87	449
TFMSA*	-	1	-	100
Benzotriazole	-	3000	-	44000
Carbamazepine	-	300	-	5000

* Relative reference value and starting concentration, no unit

For the final drinking water treatment step of the water cycle exposure route, case study data from PROMISCES were available. Data from CS1 in Berlin was used for both GAC treatment as well as for IX, and more information on the treatments can be found in (Rückbeil et al., 2025). Drinking water GAC filters usually operate to achieve high bed volumes. However, bed volumes may be intentionally reduced to ensure that certain PFAS (especially short-chain PFAS) and iPM(T)s are better removed. In this case, literature data would poorly estimate site-specific removal. To account for lower bed volume operation, experimental results of the GAC rapid small-scale column tests (RSSCT) with low bed volumes between 10,000 and 20,000 were collected as case study data. This is a good example of how case study data can be more realistic for a specific site than the general literature data. However, it is important to note that the data used came from tap water spiked with PFAS and iPM(T)s, and was from the lab-scale RSSCTs. This adds additional uncertainty to the assessment. The same applies to the experimental IX data. Data used are depicted in Table 7.

Table 7: Removal factors derived from experimental data of CS1

Substance	Removal factors in %	
	GAC (Bed volumes 10,000 – 20,000)	IX (Bed volumes 30,000 – 40,000) (only for 6 priority substances)
PFBA	8, 7, 5, 8, 4, 4, 5	
PFPeA	6, 4, 4, 15, 10, 15, 11	
PFHxA	7, 4, 9, 26, 25, 27, 32	
PFHpA	17, 12, 19, 25, 20, 29, 31	
PFOA	27, 21, 21, 39, 23, 40, 30	53, 92
PFNA	30, 17, 23, 35, 18, 59, 39	67,98
PFDA	33, 42, 34, 26, -8, 74, 34	77,99
PFBS	-9, 6, -12, 33, 26, 32, 29	
PFPeS	31, 21, 30, 42, 36, 41, 38	96, 100
PFHxS	31, 23, 31, 43, 36, 51, 39	
PFOS	33, 27, 28, 42, 18, 69, 34	98, 100
TFMSA	6, 8, 5, 15, 7, 3, -3, 4	68, 69, 48, 24
Benzotriazole	88, 89, 89, 85, 89, 88, 78, 79	
Carbamazepine	99, 98, 99, 98, 97, 94, 99, 99	

The WWTP effluent discharges into surface water and is thereby diluted. In the baseline scenario, clean surface water (no background concentrations) from a low-flow river is assumed. One part of treated wastewater (33.3%) is mixed with two parts of clean surface water (66.6%) on average. This ratio changes to 5% treated wastewater and 95% surface water in the scenarios that contain a large river. Since no site-specific data can be used for those generic assumptions, "contamination" was defined as a substance concentration twice as high as the reference value. A variation based on 20% standard deviation was integrated into the simulation. The second dilution process of the treatment train remained constant for all scenarios. Following the bank filtration process, 75% of bank filtrate is assumed to be mixed with 25% clean groundwater (Table 8).

Table 8: Dilution characteristics of the water cycle baseline scenario

Process	Average proportion of diluting water	Standard deviation of diluting water	Average pollutant concentration	Standard deviation of pollutant concentration
Dilution in a small clean river (Baseline Scenario, Scenario 1)	0.666	0.067	0	0
Dilution in a large clean river (Scenario 2)	0.95	0.025	0	0
Dilution in a small contaminated river (Scenario 4)	0.666	0.067	Twice the reference value of the substance	20% of the average concentration
Dilution in a large contaminated river (Scenario 3)	0.95	0.025	Twice the reference value of the substance	20% of the average concentration
Dilution by groundwater	0.25	0.05	0	0

4.1.1. PFOS, TFMSA and carbamazepine: HHEA result interpretation (baseline scenario)

The spider plot in Figure 10 shows the result of the baseline scenario for PFOS, TFMSA and carbamazepine. It compares the likelihood of exceeding a predefined reference value by displaying the upper part (50th to 99th percentiles) of the RQ distribution. The 75th percentiles of PFOS and TFMSA reference quotient distributions are more than tenfold higher than the reference value. Thus, there is a high probability that the reference value will be significantly exceeded. For PFOS, even the 50th percentile of the distribution is already well above the reference value. For carbamazepine, the HHEA model does not return a reference value above 1.

In the subsequent paragraphs, the interim results of the baseline scenario for the high-risk substances PFOS and TFMSA and the low-risk substance carbamazepine were compared to explain how the HHEA model works and to interpret the results. These compounds were chosen due to their different RQs and different levels knowledge.

Reference quotient (RQ) percentiles in final media

Figure 10: Spider plot of the baseline scenario for PFOS, TFMSA, and carbamazepine.

One main difference between the simulations of PFOS, TFMSA, and carbamazepine removal is the availability of literature data. While many data points for PFOS removal are listed in the HHEA data base, information about TFMSA and carbamazepine removal is missing. Despite this, the results for both substances differ significantly, which can be explained through the presence of case study data added. For all treatment processes (except GAC), the applied removal factor distribution is very similar for TFMSA and carbamazepine (Figure 11). However, the measured data for TFMSA and carbamazepine removal by GAC treatment indicate large differences in the removal efficiency (Table 7).

Figure 11: Violin plots of posterior removal factor distributions for PFOS (red), TFMSA (orange) and carbamazepine (green) along the treatment processes of the baseline scenario. Treatment IDs were defined in Table 2.

Figure 12 shows the impact of literature and measured data on the posterior distribution for GAC. The high standard deviation of PFOS literature data leads to a flat likelihood distribution. However, there is a noticeable peak of the literature – likelihood distribution at around 80%. On the contrary, the rapid small scale column test (RSSCT) results indicate a lower removal by GAC (Rückbeil et al., 2025). The posterior distribution is in between both likelihood distributions. No literature data for TFMSA or carbamazepine was collected. The data from the experiments are very contradictory, leading to almost certainly low removal for TFMSA and high removal for carbamazepine. While TFMSA is poorly removed, carbamazepine is almost certainly eliminated above 90%.

This case shows how knowledge about an individual process in the treatment train can significantly impact the outcome. GAC data is sufficient enough to rule out a risk of high exposure to carbamazepine. At the same time, TFMSA may still pose a high risk. It is thereby necessary to either collect more information on the initial concentration or removal factors of previous treatments, or to add treatments to the exposure route that effectively remove TFMSA.

Figure 12: Removal factor distribution of drinking water treatment activated carbon for A: PFOS, B: TFMSA and C: carbamazepine

The removal factor distribution of the combination of primary and secondary wastewater treatment (wwtt) is similar for all three substances, although 88 values from literature are available for PFOS and none for the other two substances. The distributions for the prior, the likelihood based on literature data, and the posterior of the PFOS removal factor during primary and secondary wastewater treatment is shown in Figure 13A. Although a lot of data is available, the posterior looks almost identical to the prior. This is due to the large range of observed removal factors in literature. Even the first 10 values of the database show a range between -105 % and 69% removal (note: negative values are treated as 0% removal in the HHEA model). Obviously, there is a huge variation in PFOS removal behaviour in different wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Thus, literature data from one WWTP can rarely be used to predict the removal in a different WWTP, and consequently, the impact of the data-derived distribution on the prior is low. The posterior distributions of TFMSA and carbamazepine are very similar, although no removal data during primary and secondary wastewater treatment is available for either substance in the database. This example shows that high uncertainty about the transferability of data (highly variable literature data) is treated similarly to missing values by the HHEA model.

Figure 13: Removal factor distributions of primary and secondary wastewater treatment for A: PFOS and B: TFMSA and carbamazepine.

For the subsequent treatments in the exposure route, removal factors from literature indicated mainly poor PFOS removal. This leads to an overall higher risk of PFOS exposure compared to TFMSA. While the lack of knowledge is responsible for the categorization of TFMSA as a priority substance, the categorization of PFOS is based on a higher certainty of poor removal along the treatment chain. The HHEA model generally classifies both situations as risky. However, the high certainty of exposure reinforces this classification.

4.1.2. All substances: baseline scenario and scenario 1

The spider plots in Figure 14 and Figure 15 show the results of the baseline scenario and scenario 1. In the baseline scenario, all percentiles of final PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFBS, benzotriazole, and carbamazepine RQs are below 1, meaning no exceedance of the reference value is expected. For PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, and PFBS, the starting concentration is already below the reference value which explains the results (Table 6). On the contrary, the removal rates along the exposure route for benzotriazole and carbamazepine are sufficient enough to achieve acceptable concentrations in drinking water.

The substances of highest concern and thereby the priority substances were PFOS, PFOA, TFMSA, PFPeS, PFDA, and PFNA, due to having an RQ > 10 at the 95th percentile, for which further scenarios according to Table 5 will be calculated.

Figure 14: Spider plot of the water cycle baseline scenario (GAC as final drinking water treatment)

The baseline scenario resembles scenario 1, in which only the final drinking water treatment was changed to ion exchange (IX). For most PFAS, this results in a slightly improved (i.e. lower) RQ. Nevertheless, the priority substances remain the same. Benzotriazole and carbamazepine are not as well removed as the PFAS. For both substances, exceeding their reference values cannot be excluded by using IX instead of GAC.

Figure 15: Spider plot of the water cycle scenario 1 (IX as final drinking water treatment)

4.1.3. Priority substances: comparing different scenarios

All scenarios for the six priority substances (PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFPeS, PFOS, TFMSA) were run. The scenarios have been given short, concise names for easier comparison.

- Baseline: GAC, small clean river
- Scenario 1: IX, small clean river
- Scenario 2: GAC, large clean river
- Scenario 3: GAC, large contaminated river
- Scenario 4: GAC, small contaminated river

The spider plots for each substance show a similar pattern (Figure 16). The use of IX instead of GAC results in a slightly more positive assessment for all priority substances. Not surprisingly, dilution with a large amount of clean surface water has the most positive effect on the result. However, even in this scenario, exceedance of the reference values cannot be excluded. What was unexpected was that for all pollutants considered here, whether the small river was contaminated or clean ("GAC, small clean river" vs. "GAC, small contaminated river") did not matter. There are two reasons for this: first, the starting concentration is set to the maximum found in the literature, which means that the specified contamination concentration (2 times the reference value) is hardly significant. Second, GAC is the critical treatment process for all priority substances. GAC is found at the end of the exposure route and therefore after the contamination event.

Figure 16: Spider plots of all water cycle scenarios for the priority substances

4.1.4. Priority substances: backwards estimation of tolerable starting concentration

As mentioned in previous sections, there is no scenario for any substance in which compliance with the reference value is certain. One of the main reasons for this is the worst-case assumption for the initial raw wastewater concentration, which is either the maximum available value in the database or 10 times the reference value. The HHEA can also be used to estimate the maximum tolerable starting concentration for a given scenario and level of knowledge. The maximum tolerable starting concentration is the input concentration at which even the 99th percentile of the RQ distribution is < 1 . To achieve this, the initial concentration is adjusted until all percentiles are green in the spider plot. For PFOA, this is the case at 15 ng/L (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Spider plot of PFOA for different starting concentrations (Baseline scenario)

The same procedure was carried out for the rest of the priority substances. The maximum tolerable starting concentrations are listed in Table 9. As more knowledge about the exposure route is gathered, this analysis can be repeated and the assessment becomes more realistic. Measured values can be directly compared to this benchmark value. This allows the HHEA to provide context for subsequent risk assessment and risk management even when there is extremely little knowledge about the substance and/or the treatment steps. A special case is the relative assessment of TFMSA. Instead of a tolerable starting concentration the simulation results in tolerable factor of a potential reference value. Thus, even substances without reference values (due to a lack of regulations or toxicological data) can be included and valuable information about the risk-based removal along the whole treatment train can be quantified and compared to other substances.

Table 9: Maximum tolerable starting concentrations in the baseline scenario

Substance	Maximum tolerable starting concentration in ng/L
PFOA	15
PFNA	1.4
PFDA	1.4
PFPeS	28
PFOS	10
TFMSA	3

4.2. Groundwater remediation

The groundwater remediation exposure route shows to which extent contaminated groundwater can be treated to make it a safe resource for drinking water. Two different groundwater treatments, persulfate based chemical oxidation with Fe(VI) and ultrasonic cavitation, are compared in two different scenarios. The treated groundwater is then mixed with uncontaminated groundwater and is finally subject to the same drinking water treatment as in the semi-closed water cycle route (aeration, rapid filtration, GAC filtration). The starting concentration is based on on-site measurements of CS7 and CS6 in which groundwater was contaminated by AFFF application. For each substance the maximum value of available measurements is used as conservative starting concentration. As the exposure route is not linked to a specific site, the assumption of the dilution by groundwater is very simple and generic: treated groundwater is mixed with an equal amount of uncontaminated groundwater (average proportion of uncontaminated groundwater 50%, standard deviation = 10%). The exposure route can be seen again in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Groundwater remediation exposure route.

For both groundwater treatment processes, measurements for different PFAS were available. In case of the persulfate oxidation the pollutant concentration was measured after two separate injection events. The removal factors were supplied as average values (Table 10). For all substances, removal factors were derived after the first infection, while only some data was available after the second injection. For some of the substances removal factors between the two infections differed significantly, for others such as PFOS a high removal could be confirmed. . Both treatment trains were

compared for all substances. If there were no measurements available, the prior was used as only input for the removal factor distribution. In the case of ultrasonic cavitation, laboratory tests look very promising for the removal of a number of PFAS, but this data could not be included in the risk assessment due to time constraints.

Following this comparison, a third scenario, in which groundwater treatment was set to a generally poor removal of all substances, was evaluated. Poor removal was defined as a 10% removal factor, which was used to build the posterior distribution. The final scenario evaluated complete absence of groundwater treatment. For the persulfate-based chemical oxidation scenario and scenarios 3 (poor removal) and 4 (no groundwater treatment), a maximum tolerable starting concentration was estimated to identify the benefits of the additional groundwater treatment compared to drinking water treatment only. The difference between the poor removal scenario and the more realistic use of measured values allows for a small qualitative sensitivity analysis of impact of groundwater treatment.

Table 10: Derived removal factors for persulfate based chemical oxidation and ultrasonic cavitation, from as yet unpublished PROMISCES deliverables

Substance	Removal factors in %		
	Starting concentration in ng/L	Persulfate based chemical oxidation	Ultrasonic cavitation
PFBA	4731	81	15
PFPeA	9969	34, 16	
PFHxA	14239	92, 77	94
PFHpA	4126	53	
PFOA	5428	61, 40	
PFNA	79	73	
PFDA	110	77, 40	
PFBS	9157	74	
PFPeS	7654	78	
PFHxS	51113	79, 18	
PFHpS	1725	56, 22	
PFOS	128600	90, 97	
4:2 FTS	50		97
6:2 FTS	6381	95, 1	100
8:2 FTS	88	86	80

It is not surprising that the risk of exceeding the limit value when producing drinking water from contaminated groundwater is high. Irrespective of the type of groundwater treatment, a large proportion of the resulting RQs are higher than 10 for almost all substances (Figure 19). This means that the reference values are very likely to be exceeded by multiple times. On the one hand, this is due to the high starting concentration, , and on the other hand, to the low level of knowledge about the removal efficiency of the treatment processes. In particular, for ultrasonic cavitation, the experimental removal factors could only be applied to a small number of substances. Accordingly, the ratio of the starting concentration to the reference value is primarily decisive for the level of the reference quotient.

Figure 19: Spider plots of the groundwater remediation (A: persulfate oxidation, B: ultrasonic cavitation) baseline scenario

In such a situation, it is more useful to use the HHEA model to estimate the maximum tolerable starting concentration (Table 11). Compared to the scenario without groundwater treatment, the tolerable PFAS concentrations increase by an average of 20% due to persulfate oxidation. This is more or less independent of the average removal factor per substance (Table 10). More importantly, it depends on the certainty of the removal performance of a treatment process. The more measured values available, the greater the effect of the site-specific likelihood on the posterior. For substances that can be easily removed, an increased quantity of measurements leads to a higher tolerable starting concentration.

The effect can be seen using the example of 6:2 FTS. A removal factor of 95% was derived for 6:2 FTS. For the groundwater remediation process, only one average value was considered, which leads to a maximum tolerable starting concentration of 8.5 ng/L to ensure a drinking water concentration below 5 ng/L. If the 95% removal is measured repeatedly 5 times, the tolerable starting concentration increases to 45 ng/L, and even to 80 ng/L if measured 10 times.

This example shows that repeated measurements can have major impacts on the result. The maximum tolerable starting concentration is more sensitive to the certainty of removal efficiency than to the existence of an initial groundwater treatment.

The results for the exposure route from contaminated groundwater to drinking water indicate that either the contamination levels in groundwater must be significantly lower than the assumed 5 µg/L

to reach the reference values, or that many additional site-specific measurements must be added to the exposure pathway to obtain a more realistic assessment.

Table 11: Tolerable starting concentrations in the groundwater remediation scenarios and the effect of persulfate based oxidation.

Substance	Maximum tolerable starting concentration in ng/L		
	Baseline scenario (persulfate based oxidation)	Scenario 2 (poor removal)	Scenario 3 (no groundwater treatment)
PFBA	167	144	136
PFPeA	152	143	136
PFHxA	1419	720	685
PFHpA	7.9	7.2	6.8
PFOA	9.1	7.2	6.8
PFNA	0.8	0.72	0.68
PFDA	0.84	0.72	0.68
PFBS	8250	7150	6850
PFPeS	14	12	11
PFHxS	12	11	11
PFHpS	3.8	3.6	3.4
PFOS	8.3	5.4	5.1
6:2 FTS	7.6	7.2	6.8
8:2 FTS	0.84	0.71	0.68

4.3. Water reuse

The water reuse exposure route involves treatment of municipal wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) effluent via advanced oxidation with E-peroxone and subsequent treatment by constructed wetlands. The treated water is then used for crop irrigation (lettuce). A total of 10 PFAS and 4 iPMT compounds have been selected for this route (Meijide Fernández et al., 2025) (Table 12). The exposure route can be seen again in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Water reuse exposure route.

Table 12: List of 10 PFAS and 4 iPMT that have been considered for the water reuse route.

PFAS		iPMT	
PFHxA	Perfluorohexanoic acid	DEP	Diethyl phthalate
PFPeA	Perfluoropentanoic acid	DBP	Dibutyl phthalate
PFBS	Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid	CBZ	Carbamazepine
PFBA	Perfluorobutanoic acid	Diuron	Diuron
PFDA	Perfluorodecanoic acid		
PFNA	Perfluorononanoic acid		
PFOS	Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid		
PFOA	Perfluorooctanoic acid		
PFHpA	Perfluoroheptanoic acid		
PFHxS	Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid		

As previously explained, although this exposure route ends in human consumption of lettuce, the HHEA model is only operated on the water matrix. After the municipal wastewater treatment, the treatment via E-peroxone and the treatment via constructed wetlands, two additional processes were implemented: dilution by irrigation water (dilrw) and concentration by evaporation (sepev). This enables calculation of the final concentration in the soil pore water. Using PFOA as example substance here, the concentration in the pore water is evaluated against the reference value for PFOA to obtain the reference quotient. The variable definitions are shown in Table 13.

Table 13: Variable definition for water reuse route – PFOA example.

Variable	Value
treatment_train	["wwtt", "wwel", "wetl", "dilrw", "sepev"]
substance	"pfoa"
case_study_name	"water reuse"
scenario_name	"standard"
input_matrix	rww
n_runs	10 000
removal_factor_resolution	1000 (--> resolution of 0.1% removal factor steps)

Starting concentrations have been calculated as mean values for all literature and site-specific concentrations in the WWTP inlet. The implemented starting concentrations for each compound of water reuse route can be seen in Table 14.

Table 14: implemented starting concentrations for water reuse route.

Substance	Number of data (N)	Value (ng/L)
PFDA	47	1.8
PFNA	49	2.8
PFOS	28	61.7
PFOA	60	26.7
PFHXS	24	11.7
PFHPA	49	4.6
PFHXA	45	15.5
PFPEA	37	3.6
PFBS	49	19.1
PFBA	35	4.6
DEP	4	2538
DBP	4	657.3
CBZ	5	39.8
Diuron	4	21.4

The mixing process characteristics can be found in Table 15, where x is the proportion of the added or removed water, c is the PFOA concentration of the external water in ng/L (0 ng/L was the default), the RO concentrate data come from (Lancioni et al., 2023) and the dilution by municipal wastewater is an estimate calculated with site data from (Meijide Fernández et al., 2025). A total evapotranspiration ranging from 0.39 to 1.19 l/hour was lost due to evapotranspiration in an inflow rate ranging from 11.43 to 18.0 l/hours, obtaining an evapotranspiration from 2 to 10% of inflow water.

Table 15: Mixing process characteristics for the water reuse route for all scenarios.

Water	x_{mean}	x_{sd}	c_{mean}	c_{sd}	Comments
Irrigation water dilution (dilrw)	0	0	0	0	Implemented but no dilution is applied on field
Evaporation water (sepev)	0.21	0.015	0	0	Upper range of evapotranspiration from site data (Meijide Fernández et al., 2025)

As results show, the reference value for PFOA in the pore water is sometimes exceeded in the baseline scenario (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Modelled removal factors and concentration profile for PFOA in the water reuse route.

A spider plot of all compounds evaluated under the baseline scenario is shown in Figure 22. Among the 14 substances, four (PFDA, PFOS, PFOA and PFHxS) posed an unacceptable risk in most of the samples. Although within acceptable risk thresholds, PFNA would exceed 10% of the reference value with a 25% probability, while PFHxA would do so in 5% of cases.

Figure 22: Spider plot for all 14 substances of water reuse route.

Modelling results for all substances are in Annex I. See PROMISCES Deliverable D5.4 (Narain-Ford et al., 2024) for further information on DEP and PFBS exposure route and risk assessment.

PFOA and PFOS were selected for further scenario assessment. Four scenarios were assessed, combining low/high starting concentrations (inlet) and poor/good performance of the electro-oxidation treatment (E-peroxone), and results for PFOA are shown in Figure 23 and Figure 24. The assumed values for each scenario can be seen in Table 16.

It should be noted that site values by (Meijide Fernández et al., 2025) show a wide deviation from the mean, even extending into negative ranges. This is mainly due to the fact that certain treatments apparently increase (rather than reduce) the concentration of certain compounds. This is because some compounds are generated during the treatment as a degradation process of other, more

complex compounds, for which a decrease in concentrations and a positive removal factor are observed.

Table 16: Changing parameters for the different water reuse scenarios.

	PFOA		PFOS		Comments
	Mean	σ	Mean	σ	
Standard					
Raw wastewater concentration (ng/L)	26.7	75.2	61.7	78.9	All literature and site data considered.
E-peroxone removal rate (wwel) (%)	28.4	41.3	14.2	60.3	All literature and site data considered.
Scenario 1: Poor performance, High inlet concentrations					
Raw wastewater concentration (ng/L)	77.4		114.9		Value = 75% normal distribution.
E-peroxone removal rate (wwel) (%)	0.6		-26.5		Value = 25% normal distribution.
Scenario 2: Poor performance, Low inlet concentrations					
Raw wastewater concentration (ng/L)	1.0		8.5		Value = 75% normal distribution (minimum 1 ng/L)
E-peroxone removal rate (wwel) (%)	0.6		-26.5		Value = 25% normal distribution.
Scenario 3: Good performance, High inlet concentrations					
Raw wastewater concentration (ng/L)	77.4		114.9		Value = 75% normal distribution.
E-peroxone removal rate (wwel) (%)	56.3		54.9		Value = 25% normal distribution.
Scenario 4: Good performance, Low inlet concentrations					
Raw wastewater concentration (ng/L)	1.0		8.5		Value = 25% normal distribution (minimum 1 ng/L)
E-peroxone removal rate (wwel) (%)	56.3		54.9		Value = 75% normal distribution.

Note: Negative removal rates are considered to be zero by the tool.

Figure 23: Modelled PFOA concentration profiles in the water reuse exposure route for the baseline scenario (Std) and 4 adapted scenarios. The reference value is 6 ng/L PFOA.

Reference quotient (RQ) percentiles in final media

Figure 24: Modelled PFOA RQ for the water reuse exposure route for the baseline scenario (Std) and 4 adapted scenarios.

Scenarios 1 and 3, which share high inlet concentrations, would result in unsafe concentrations under these conditions. Poor performance of the E-peroxone treatment (scenarios 2 and 4) poses a less critical risk to human health than probable high starting concentrations.

The PFOS spider plot (see Annex I) shows a worsening in risk mainly due to a lower reference value, with no scenario showing $RQ < 1$ above the 50th percentile.

4.4. Nutrient recovery

The nutrient recovery exposure route is based on pre-treatment of landfill leachate before it is mixed with municipal wastewater so that the final dewatered sludge from the wastewater treatment plant can be used as a fertilizer for agriculture. A total of 7 PFAS has been considered for this route: PFOA, PFHpA, PFHxS, PFHxA, PFPeA, PFBS and PFBA. No iPMT compounds were monitored in this route. PFOA was used to illustrate this route because it has been well studied in literature and data for it could be obtained. The exposure route can be seen again in Figure 25.

Figure 25: Nutrient recovery exposure route.

A more detailed definition of the exposure can be found in PROMISCES deliverable D4.5 (Lancioni et al., 2023) which described three different combinations of landfill and municipal wastewater treatment in Italy, and reported the sampling results from different campaigns. For the implementation as treatment train into the HHEA model, plant no. 3 from D4.5 was selected. In the plant, the landfill leachate is first pre-treated with flotation, sand filters, and ultrafiltration. The water is then treated with reverse osmosis (RO). The concentrate is further processed by flocculation with a sand filter and stripping before it is mixed again with the RO permeate. There are therefore two parallel routes within the treatment train, consisting of RO concentrate and RO permeate, which posed a challenge for the application of the HHEA model. It was decided to integrate the permeate (main flow: 1340 m³/d) into the exposure path and to add the concentrate flow (215 m³/d) via a mixing process afterwards. The effluent is then discharged into the sewer system and mixed with municipal wastewater before it reaches the municipal WWTP. Municipal wastewater treatment consists of primary and secondary treatment. It is assumed that PFAS that do not leave the wastewater treatment plant via the liquid phase and rather remain in the sludge (see section 4.5), which is then used agriculturally as fertiliser. As with the water reuse route, this is followed by two additional processes, dilution by irrigation water and concentration by evaporation, to reach the final concentration in the soil pore water. The concentration in the pore water is evaluated against the reference value for PFOA to obtain the reference quotient. The input variables are described in Table 17.

Table 17: Variable definition for nutrient recovery route.

Variable	Value
treatment_train	["wwt1", "wwnf", "wwro", "dilpr", "dilww", "wwsl", "dilrw", "sepev"]
substance	"pfoa"
case_study_name	"nutrient_recovery"
scenario_name	"standard", "cont_irrigation"
input_matrix	iww (industrial wastewater)
n_runs	10 000
removal_factor_resolution	1000 (--> resolution of 0.1% removal factor steps)

The initial concentration in landfill leachate was derived from on-site measurements (Lancioni et al., 2023) and literature values. The mean values implemented can be seen in Table 18.

Table 18: implemented starting concentrations for the nutrient recovery route:

Substance	Number of data (N)	Value (ng/L)
PFHPA	9	9.8
PFPEA	4	9.8
PFBS	5	167.6
PFBA	6	4.8
PFOA	8	57.9
PFHXS	8	25.7
PFHXA	7	40.9

The first process (primary treatment) is based solely on literature values and leads to a reduction in the PFOA concentration below the calculated reference value in pore water. This is followed by mixing with the treated RO permeate, with literature and site-specific data from (Lancioni et al., 2023). Determining a fixed mixing ratio is challenging because it is site-specific and depends on the characteristics of both the RO permeate (removal efficiency) and the WWTP influent. The mixing conditions applied with the permeate (dilpr), as well as with municipal wastewater (dilww), to dewatered sludge (wwsl), with irrigation water (dilrw) and the concentration due to evaporation (sepev) in the soil are described in Table 19. In the table, x is the proportion of the added or removed water, c is the PFOA concentration of the external source of water in ng/L). RO concentrate data come from (Lancioni et al., 2023), the dilution by municipal wastewater is an estimate, and evaporation of irrigation water was assigned a conservative value (twice the value reported in the wetlands for the previous water reuse route) due to the lack of site-specific data.

Table 19: Characteristics of mixing processes of the nutrient recovery route.

Water	X _{mean}	X _{sd}	C _{mean}	C _{sd}	Comments
Scenario: Standard					
RO concentrate	0.16	0.016	0	0	x standard deviation assumed to be 10% of mean value, process water characteristics based on (Lancioni et al, 2023)
Municipal wastewater	0.875	0.038	0	0	x entered as range between 0.8 and 0.95
Wastewater to dewatered sludge	0.30	0	0	0	assuming that all sludge contaminant migrates to 30% porosity
Irrigation water	0.99993	5.5E-06	0	0	x entered as range between 0.9993 and 0.9996
Evaporation water	0.21	0.015	0	0	x entered as range between 0.18 and 0.24

The dilution with irrigation water is >99.9% and is therefore extremely high. The calculation is based on the following assumptions:

1. The application of sludge as fertiliser is based on the P requirement of the soil. A high requirement of 60 kg P₂O₅/ha soil was assumed (worst case assumption).
2. It was also assumed that the P₂O₅ content of the sludge corresponds to 10%. This means that 6 kg/ha or 0.06 kg sludge/ m² soil are applied.
3. As the HHEA model works on a volume basis, the application amount was converted into a volume of 0.067 L /m² by using a sludge density of 0.9 kg/L.
4. 100 to 200 litres of water per m² are used within the lettuce growing period.

This assumption leads to a volume-related proportion of irrigation water between 99.93% and 99.966%. Evaporation was also estimated as described for the water reuse exposure route.

Concentration profiles show that PFOA is reduced to values below the reference value after the primary treatment (wwt1). Reference value for PFOA is set at 6 ng/L in pore water. Results can be seen in Figure 26.

Figure 26: Modelled removal factors and concentration profile of nutrient recovery route for PFOA.

A spider plot of all compounds evaluated under baseline (standard) conditions is shown in Figure 27. All 7 PFAS pose low risk in most of the cases ($RQ \leq 0.1$ at $\geq 99^{\text{th}}$ percentile). Modelling results for all substances are in Annex II. See PROMISCES Deliverable D5.4 (Narain-Ford et al., 2024) for further information regarding PFBS exposure route and risk assessment.

Reference quotient (RQ) percentiles in final media

Figure 27: Spider plot for all 7 PFAS in nutrient recovery route.

Three substances (PFOA, PFHxS, PFHxA) were selected for further analysis in four additional scenarios. The scenarios combined poor/good performances of leachate treatment removal rate and nanofiltration. All scenarios considered poor WWTP performance. The assumed values for each scenario can be found in Table 20. The results thereof can be seen in Figure 28.

Table 20: Changing parameters for the different scenarios of the nutrient recovery route.

	PFOA		PFHxS		PFHxA		Comments
	Mean	σ	Mean	σ	Mean	σ	
Standard							
Leachate treatment removal rate (wwt1) (%)	-18.5	50.0	1.6	15.0	-70.8	154.5	Only literature data available.
Nanofiltration removal rate (wwnf) (%)	92.3	11.9	99.9	0.2	86.8	19.9	All literature and site data considered.
Wastewater treatment (wwsl) (%)	30.0	0.0	30.0	0.0	30.0	0.0	Estimated parameter
Scenario 1: Leachate treatment poor performance, Nanofiltration poor performance, Wastewater treatment poor performance							
Leachate treatment removal rate (wwt1) (%)	-52.2		-8.5		-174.9		Value = 25% normal distribution.
Nanofiltration removal rate (wwnf) (%)	84.3		99.8		73.3		Value = 25% normal distribution.
Wastewater treatment (wwsl) (%)	90.0	0.0	90.0	0.0	90.0	0.0	Near 100% value
Scenario 2: Leachate treatment good performance, Nanofiltration poor performance, Wastewater treatment poor performance							
Leachate treatment removal rate (wwt1) (%)	15.3		11.7		33.4		Value = 75% normal distribution.
Nanofiltration removal rate (wwnf) (%)	84.3		99.8		73.3		Value = 25% normal distribution.
Wastewater treatment (wwsl) (%)	90.0	0.0	90.0	0.0	90.0	0.0	Near 100% value
Scenario 3: Leachate treatment poor performance, Nanofiltration good performance, Wastewater treatment poor performance							
Leachate treatment removal rate (wwt1) (%)	-52.2		-8.5		-174.9		Value = 25% normal distribution.
Nanofiltration removal rate (wwnf) (%)	99.9		99.9		99.9		Value = 75% normal distribution (max. 99.9%).
Wastewater treatment (wwsl) (%)	90.0	0.0	90.0	0.0	90.0	0.0	Near 100% value

Scenario 4: Leachate treatment good performance, Nanofiltration good performance, Wastewater treatment poor performance							
Leachate treatment removal rate (wwt1) (%)	15.3		11.7		33.4		Value = 75% normal distribution.
Nanofiltration removal rate (wwnf) (%)	99.9		99.9		99.9		Value = 75% normal distribution (max. 99.9%).
Wastewater treatment (wwsl) (%)	90.0	0.0	90.0	0.0	90.0	0.0	Near 100% value

Note: Negative removal rates are considered by the tool as zero.

Figure 28: Modelled concentration profiles of nutrient recovery route – scenarios 1 to 4. Reference value is estimated at 6 ng/L PFOA.

All scenarios, including the baseline (standard) simulation, show low risk (Figure 29). High removal efficiencies of primary treatment (wwt1) or NF (wwnf) and RO (wwro) reduce RQ to values far below 0.1 for all probabilities. Similar risk outputs are obtained for PFHxS and PFHxA (see Annex II).

Figure 29: Modelled reference quotient diagram along the nutrient recovery route for PFOA in 4 different scenarios.

4.5.Code availability

The .ipynb and .csv files for the four routes investigated have been published on GitHub (<https://github.com/KWB-R/promisces.hhea/>) and a link is also available on Zenodo.

5. Discussion and conclusions

This deliverable describes the development and operation of the HHEA model. It describes the infrastructure, the operation and theory behind the probabilistic Bayesian updating approach, and explains how the model was applied to the 4 CE routes investigated in PROMISCES.

For each CE route, the uncertainty of the risk of certain PFAS/iPM(T) of greatest concern were quantified. These compounds were determined by running a baseline scenario and observing which compounds had the highest RQ value. These compounds were subsequently analysed through 4 additional scenarios, to determine how changes in the exposure route would change the RQ. This was done so that the HHEA will improve understanding of decision making and risk management under uncertainty related to fate, exposure, and hazard.

For the semi-closed water cycle exposure route, six priority substances which had RQs > 1 for at least one percentile in the baseline scenario were identified (PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFPeS, PFOS, TFMSA). By running scenarios with different sizes and background contamination of rivers and/or different final drinking water treatment technologies, dilution had the most significant effect on compound reduction. Additionally, it was revealed that GAC as final drinking water treatment could notably reduce compound concentrations regardless of whether the discharged effluent entered a small, clean river or a small, contaminated river.

For the groundwater remediation exposure route, which was purely evaluated for modelling purposes, as contaminated groundwater would not be used for drinking water production, results were unlike the other exposure routes. The RQs of all evaluated compounds were multiple times greater than 1, due to the general assumption of a 5 µg/L concentration for each compound, as well as lack of knowledge of compound removal in the treatment processes. For this route, the ratio of the starting concentration to the reference value overwhelmingly dictated the RQ. Therefore, maximum tolerable starting concentrations which would lead to a maximum concentration of 5 ng/L in drinking water were calculated backwards. The more measurements there are confirming high removal (95%), the higher the maximum tolerable starting concentration could be: repeated measurements can have major impacts on the result. The maximum tolerable starting concentration was more sensitive to certainty of removal efficiency than to groundwater treatment.

For the water reuse exposure route, six substances presented RQs > 1 for all percentiles (PFDA, PFNA, PFOS, PFOA, PFHxS and PFHxA). Subsequent scenarios analyses on PFOA and PFOS revealed that poor performance of the E-peroxone treatment posed less of a risk than high inlet concentrations for PFOA, whereas for PFOS, no scenario achieved RQ < 1 above the 50th percentile, primarily due to the lower reference value.

For the nutrient recovery exposure route, all percentiles of all 7 PFAS compounds showed RQ ≤ 1. For subsequent scenarios analyses, especially high PFAS removal during membrane filtration resulted in similar low RQ values (RQ ≤ 1).

The HHEA model addressed epistemic uncertainty, meaning uncertainty of the model via lack of training data, by differentiating how likelihood and posterior distributions are affected based on the literature data evaluated. One study presenting poor removal has a greater effect on the likelihood

and posterior distribution than one study presenting good removal, thereby facilitating a risk-based approach where more evidence is needed to verify a high removal. To balance this out, when site-specific data are included in the assessment, if the difference in removal factors is expected to average out over time, removal factors and input concentrations are combined randomly to prevent under or over estimation of exposure via worst case or best case scenario assessment.

The influence of literature, measured, and modelled data on the HHEA model outcome is substantial, as both the availability and variability of data directly shape the posterior removal factor distributions and ultimately the risk classification. This was demonstrated using compounds PFOS, TFMSA and carbamazepine in the semi-closed water cycle exposure route. For PFOS, abundant but highly variable literature data results in wide, flat likelihood distributions, limiting the model's ability to update priors and reducing predictive certainty across treatment stages. In contrast, the absence of literature data for TFMSA and carbamazepine is partially offset by measured data, which drives distinct model outcomes—low removal for TFMSA and high for carbamazepine—particularly in GAC treatment. This highlights how localized, high-quality data can significantly refine model predictions. Moreover, the model treats highly uncertain or variable literature data similarly to missing data, reinforcing the need for representative, transferable datasets. Ultimately, the model differentiates between risk driven by data gaps (e.g., TFMSA) and risk driven by well-documented poor removal (e.g., PFOS), demonstrating how both the quantity and quality of input data critically affect exposure assessment and prioritization.

In the future, data from other models developed in PROMISCES (Groot et al., 2025; Zessner et al., 2025) providing concentrations or in silico parameters could also be integrated into the HHEA modelling. The Decision Support Framework (DSF) Tool developed in PROMISCES (<https://promisces.eu/Results/Tools/PROMISCES+DSF.html>) also links to the HHEA model. By providing exposure assessment as part of the DSF tool, users can access the pre-evaluated 4 exposure routes described in this report for an initial assessment of how PFAS are removed in the exposure routes. When users download the HHEA model to their local environment, all parameters can be changed, and additional data can be included in the HHEA assessment, providing users with a more site-specific assessment of PFAS and iPMT exposure.

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Annexes

Annex I. Water reuse simulation outputs

Annex II. Nutrient recovery simulation outputs

Substance	Baseline simulation
<p style="text-align: center;">PFBA</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">At CS '4' - 'PFBA Std.'</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">PFOA</p>	

